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Operando Cryogenic Processing Effects on Residual Stress and Magnetism of Martensitic Stainless Steel for Energy Sector

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Abstract

Martensitic stainless steels (MSS) are widely used in the energy sector due to their high hardenability, corrosion resistance, and favourable mechanical properties. Their performance in extreme environments—such as fusion reactors, offshore systems, and hydrogen infrastructure—depends strongly on the interplay between microstructure, residual stresses, and resulting properties, including magnetic behaviour and mechanical strength. In fusion applications, neutron irradiation and high magnetic fields can significantly alter MSS microstructure, potentially compromising material stability and leading to component failure. To enhance microstructural stability under such conditions, advanced processing methods are required. Cryogenic processing (CP), which involves exposing materials to temperatures below 77 K, has shown promise in improving properties like hardness and corrosion resistance through microstructural refinement. However, the underlying mechanisms governing these improvements, particularly in MSS for energy applications, remain insufficiently understood. Existing studies indicate that CP can influence magnetic properties and residual stresses, but comprehensive operando investigations, especially under strong magnetic fields, are lacking. This study investigates the effects of CP on MSS EN X17CrNi16-2 under different treatment conditions, including conventional heat treatment, CP, and CP combined with magnetic field exposure up to 5 T. The work examines micro-residual stresses (ex-situ and in-situ), magnetic behaviour using advanced microscopy techniques, and mechanical properties via microhardness testing. Additionally, it provides novel insights into the time-dependent mechanisms of CP through advanced neutron measurements, contributing to a deeper understanding of structure–property relationships in MSS for future energy applications.

Keywords

energy sector, martensitic stainless steel, magnetism, residual stresses, operando measurements, WOMBAT, POLDI, MOKE

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Abstract

Martensitic stainless steels (MSS) are widely used in the energy sector due to their high hardenability, corrosion resistance, and favourable mechanical properties. Their performance in extreme environments—such as fusion reactors, offshore systems, and hydrogen infrastructure—depends strongly on the interplay between microstructure, residual stresses, and resulting properties, including magnetic behaviour and mechanical strength. In fusion applications, neutron irradiation and high magnetic fields can significantly alter MSS microstructure, potentially compromising material stability and leading to component failure. To enhance microstructural stability under such conditions, advanced processing methods are required. Cryogenic processing (CP), which involves exposing materials to temperatures below 77 K, has shown promise in improving properties like hardness and corrosion resistance through microstructural refinement. However, the underlying mechanisms governing these improvements, particularly in MSS for energy applications, remain insufficiently understood. Existing studies indicate that CP can influence magnetic properties and residual stresses, but comprehensive operando investigations, especially under strong magnetic fields, are lacking. This study investigates the effects of CP on MSS EN X17CrNi16-2 under different treatment conditions, including conventional heat treatment, CP, and CP combined with magnetic field exposure up to 5 T. The work examines micro-residual stresses (*ex-situ* and *in-situ*), magnetic behaviour using advanced microscopy techniques, and mechanical properties via microhardness testing. Additionally, it provides novel insights into the time-dependent mechanisms of CP through advanced neutron measurements, contributing to a deeper understanding of structure–property relationships in MSS for future energy applications.

Keywords: energy sector, martensitic stainless steel, magnetism, residual stresses, operando measurements, WOMBAT, POLDI, MOKE

1. Introduction

Martensitic stainless steels (MSS) are commonly used in the energy sector due to their hardenability, good corrosion resistance in highly corrosive environments, and their mechanical properties (especially hardness) [1–4]. MSS are widely applicable in various energy sectors, including oil and gas, hydropower (e.g. turbines), wind energy, and emerging energy sectors such as fusion [5,6]. The correlation between microstructure, residual stresses and final properties (e.g. corrosion resistance, magnetic behaviour and mechanical properties) is crucial for applications in extreme conditions, such as in the energy sector (e.g. offshore energy [7], geothermal energy [8] and fusion energy[9,10]), the hydrogen infrastructure sector [11–13], the aerospace sector and space systems [14–16], the medical sector [17], and the automotive industry, with an emphasis on the green and e-mobility transitions [18]. Previous studies on ferro-martensitic (RAFM) and martensitic stainless steels have shown that there is a strong correlation between microstructure, residual stress, mechanical properties and magnetic behaviour in the fusion sector [19–23] of the material. When MSS are exposed to neutrons, the interrelations between microstructure and material properties are critical. This is because the microstructure of MSS can be altered during exposure to a fusion reactor due to high-energy particles (irradiation), which induce microstructural changes [4,19,24]. These changes affect the final properties, which can lead to changes in the crystal structure of the material. This influences the stability of the material, which can result in failure of the material and components. This can lead to failure of the reactor and the need for unplanned maintenance [24,25]. In future fusion reactors, reactor magnets (e.g. Nb₃Sn or NbTi) will produce magnetic fields of 5-20 T, which will additionally contribute to faster degradation of the materials [26,27].

To stabilise the microstructure and dimensions of the MSS and ensure it can withstand exposure to extreme conditions in future fusion reactors, various heat treatment and processing techniques are employed [9,11,28–31]. Cryogenic Processing (CP) is one of the options available. During CP, the material is exposed to cryogenic temperatures (usually below 77 K) for a certain duration. This process changes the material's microstructure and nanoscopic features, ultimately affecting its final properties [32–42]. A plethora of studies have demonstrated the positive influence of CP on different alloys (ferrous and non-ferrous) and the enhancement of various properties (corrosion resistance, hardness, strength etc.) [32,43–47]. However, despite the promising potential of this new processing method, research in this area is perceived to be lacking, particularly with regard to the mechanisms driving the individual changes in structural steels for energy sector. Some studies have been done on how structural steels behave when they are exposed to cryogenic temperatures. These studies looked at how the steels' behaviour and magnetic properties changed when they were exposed to subzero temperatures [48–50], which is not the same as CP. There are some studies, which actually tested magnetic behaviour of ferrous alloys after CP, which showed changes in magnetic hardness and coercivity [9,48,51–53], which was related to changes in residual stresses [9].

Also, there has been a lack of any advanced studies (*operando*) of magnets on materials used (above 200 mT) in the energy industry to see how the materials behave when they are used. Consequently, it is imperative to undertake a comprehensive investigation into the impact of CP on MSS used in future energy sector(s), such as fusion, encompassing the induced alterations in microstructure and ultimate properties. This is particularly interesting when it comes to understanding the relationship between the underlying sub-micrometre microstructural features and defects and the magnetic domain structures and overall magnetic properties in correlation to residual stresses. These properties can act as indicators and figures of merit for the selected properties, and understanding the underlying mechanism of CP on ferrous alloys could help to tailor different alloys.

This study focuses on the effect of CP on selected MSS EN X17CrNi16-2 a in regards to different heat treatments (conventional, CP and CP exposed to magnetic field to 5 T), including micro-residual stresses *ex-situ* and *in-situ* observation, as well as its magnetic behaviour (with magnetic force microscopy and magneto-optical Kerr effect microscopy) and mechanical behaviour (microhardness). Furthermore, this study presents one of the first observations of the underlying time-dependent CP mechanism, as determined by advanced neutron measurements.

2. Methods

a. Material, processing, microstructure and phase analysis

The proposed cryogenically tailored ferrous alloy was EN X17CrNi16-2 a Cr-rich ferrous alloy (chemical composition in wt. %: 0.16 C, 0.81 Mn, 0.02 S, 0.04 P, 0.30 Si, 0.10 Mo, 1.55 Ni, 15.25 Cr, Fe base other elements below 0.1) from producer ESG Edelstahl-Scheidservice GmbH. The samples were divided into 2 subgroups a control group marked C and a test group marked T. The temperature of austenitisation was fixed at $T_a = 1303$ K / 0.5 h and quenching rate (1073-773 K) ~ 10 K/s, afterwards the control subgroup MSS-C was subjected to 1 cycle of tempering at 753 K / 2 h, whereas the other test subgroup MSS-T was subjected to CP for 24 h at 77 K followed by 1 cycle of tempering at 753 K / 2 h. Another test group was subjected to CP for 8 h (MSS-8 h) at 77 K followed by 1 cycle of tempering at 753 K / 2 h and another was exposed to multicycling (8 h at 77 K + 6 h at 294 K + 8 h at 77 K) (MSS-multicycling) by 1 cycle of tempering at 753 K / 2 h (Table 1).

Table 1: The heat treatment parameters for all subgroups are shown below. MSS-C is the control group with no CP application and MSS-T/MSS-8 h/ MSS-multicycling are the test groups with CP application.

Sample Group	Austenitisation (T_a in K)	Cryogenic processing (time/temperature)	Tempering (T_t in K)
MSS-C	1303 / 0.5 h	No	753 K / 2 h
MSS-24 h	1303 / 0.5 h	24 h / 77 K	753 K / 2 h
MSS-8 h	1303 / 0.5 h	8 h / 77 K	753 K / 2 h
MSS-multicycling	1303 / 0.5 h	8 h + 8 h / 77 K	753 K / 2 h

All specimens were heat treated at the Max Planck Institute for Sustainable Materials (MPI SusMat), Germany. All samples were heat treated in an Ar atmosphere under high vacuum. Samples were metallographically prepared for further analysis according to Jovičević-Klug et al 2021 [54] for the preparation of cryogenically processed ferrous alloys. The microstructural analysis of the EN X17CrNi16-2 ferrous alloy was performed using a Zeiss Crossbeam Merlin I scanning electron microscope (SEM) at MPI SusMat. A Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer with a Cu $K\alpha$ X-ray source was used for quantitative phase analysis. The diffractometer is equipped with micro area optics (500 μ m x 500 μ m beam size), 5-circle goniometer and HyPix3000 area detector. Measurements were performed as a continuous symmetric overview scan with a step size of $\Delta 2\theta = 0.01^\circ$, a count rate of 4°/min and a power setup of 45kV/200mA. Rietveld simulation was used to quantify each phase from the measured data.

b. In-house surface micro-residual stresses

Micro-residual stress measurements were carried out using a Rigaku SmartLab equipped with a Cu $K\alpha$ rotating anode X-ray source. This diffractometer is equipped with a micro-area beam optic (beam size: 500 μ m by 500 μ m), a five-circle goniometer and a HyPix3000 area detector. A residual stress measurement was performed for each sample for the major phases (weight fraction >10%). The 2θ position of a reflection selected for each phase was measured at 13 different sample tilt angles ($\chi = -63.5^\circ$ to $+63.5^\circ$) and three different stress directions ($\Theta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 90°). The 2θ position was then used to calculate the residual stress according to the $\sin^2\psi$ method [55].

c. Atom probe tomography (APT)

Atom probe tomography (APT) specimens were prepared by two-stage electropolishing using perchloric acid, first in glacial acetic acid then in 2-butoxyethanol. The specimens were analysed using a Cameca Invivo 6000 operated in laser-pulsed mode, with 300 pJ pulse energy, 200 kHz repetition rate, 50 K base temperature, and 4% target detection rate. Data reconstruction and analysis was performed using AP Suite 6.3. Crystallographic features on the detector were used to determine the field and image compression factors and to spatially-calibrate the reconstruction.

d. Microhardness with Vickers

Microhardness of samples obtained after different heat treatment procedures was measured using Vickers HV30 method at room temperature (21 $^\circ$ C and 50 % humidity). For each subgroup multiple measurements were performed on several specimens (at least 6) and the average value was calculated.

e. High-Intensity powder diffractometer (WOMBAT)

WOMBAT is a high-intensity neutron diffractometer located in the OPAL Neutron Guide Hall at ANSTO (Australia's Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation) in Australia [56]. It is primarily used as a high-speed powder diffractometer, but it can be also used for texture characterisation and single-crystal measurement, particularly diffuse scattering. The cylindrical 2D detector of 728 mm radius is $120^\circ \times 200$ mm high, with vertical wires spaced 0.125° apart and maximum angle of 160° [56,57]. This study required *in-situ* measurement of phase transformations and crystallography information across the temperature range of 77 K to 753 K, analysis of cm-scale volumes, measurement of grains that may exhibit significant texturing, and kinetic information over timescales of 1–5 minutes. Samples of EN X17CrNi16-2 a, quenched and pre-cut into 10 mm diameter, ≈ 10 mm long cylinders were used for this testing. Figure 1 shows the heat treatments which were performed on each sample and the stages at which neutron diffraction patterns were recorded. The first sample ('MSS-C sample') was analysed using WOMBAT while being heated to 753 K for 2 h. The second sample ('MSS-24 h sample') was analysed while being cooled to 77 K for 24 h then while being heated to 753 K for 2 h. The third sample ('MSS-24 h+mag sample') was analysed while being cooled to 77 K in a 5 T magnetic field 5T for 24 h, then while being heated to 753 K for 2 h. The raw 2D diffraction patterns were processed using LAMP. Corrections were made for the cylindrical response function and the projection of the Debye–Scherrer cones onto the detector. The patterns were then vertically integrated to produce 1D diffraction patterns, which were analysed using Rietveld refinement. If texturing was significant, qualitative phase analysis was performed using the corrected 2D diffraction patterns. 10 min integration times were chosen from point to point, except for the DCT magnetic field (DCT mag) where the cooling and heating was probed with 15/20 min intervals. The wavelength was 1.22 \AA and the scan range was from 15° to 134° . The position of peaks was determined by fitting the individual peaks with a Gaussian function after which the position of the peaks was defined by the center of mass of the peak bounded by the statistical evaluation of the peak data in the range of the full width at half maximum width. This enables averaging of the potential skewness and asymmetric contribution in the case of refinement of grain size and micro-strain changes while also minimizing the peak position variation caused by local noise.

Figure 1: Heat treatments for a conventional heat treatment (MSS-C) sample, a deep cryogenic treatment (MSS-24 h) sample, and a DCT sample with a magnetic field applied (MSS-24 h+mag at 5 T). The shaded regions indicate the stages that were analysed *in-situ* using WOMBAT. The transparent stages were performed prior to arrival at ANSTO.

f. Pulse OverLap Diffractometer (POLDI)

Pulse OverLap Diffractometer (POLDI) is a time-of-flight thermal neutron diffractometer, dedicated to spatially resolved measurements of residual stresses at the continuous spallation source SINQ at Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) in Switzerland. At POLDI, the continuous neutron beam is transformed into a pulsed beam using a multi-slit chopper, whose 700 mm disc with 32 slits creates a 5.8% duty cycle and operates at speeds up to 15,000 rpm. The beam is then guided over about 12 m and focused onto the sample using an elliptical neutron guide, with diaphragms and collimators controlling divergence, beam size, and gauge volume. Diffracted neutrons are measured by a one-dimensional position-sensitive ^3He detector with 400 wires, providing angular coverage of 30° horizontally and 6.4° vertically [58]. POLDI instrument was used in this experiment in order to identify the changes of residual

stresses during CP in correlation to the microstructure evolution, which can influence the final properties of the material and then component. Cylindrical samples of 6 mm diameter and 5 mm length were prepared and heat treated at the MPI-SusMat to the point of quenching. First, the quenched samples were measured at room temperature (measuring all 3 normal strain components) to attain a reference point of the stress state of the material. To decouple the effects of composition and strain, a “strain-free” sample was measured. After the reference states were measured, the samples were analysed *in-situ* during exposure to 77 K for 24 h in an ILL-type Orange cryostat. During this procedure the strain change was measured in 10 min intervals at which two samples were measured simultaneously. Afterwards, the samples were measured at room temperature again, in order to have an intermediate stress state that allowed the correlation of the strain change to the stress change during the *in-situ* measurements. Afterwards, the samples were investigated *in-situ* during tempering at 753 K using the Ta furnace. Strain measurements were performed at 4 min intervals to indicate the development of residual stresses during tempering/aging. However, the integration of multiple intervals (at least 2) was required to obtain sufficient signal to noise ratio for the raw data fitting and reliable strain measurements. During the *in-situ* CP and tempering measurements, the monitoring of the radial strain component of the samples was performed. Finally, all samples were investigated at room temperature to indicate the final stress state with relation to the different heat treatment conditions and handling. For the data analysis the two-dimensional fitting of raw data (intensity versus angle and arrival time), was implemented in MANTID program [59] based on the outlined principle. For the strain evaluation the Pawley fitting was used. For the strain characterization along each principal direction the (211) peak was evaluated and the strain was calculated by Equation 1:

$$\varepsilon(211) = \frac{d(211) - d_0(211)}{d_0(211)}$$

The strain was recalculated as stress values for each principal direction following the modified Hooke's Law. Equation 2:

$$\sigma_x = \frac{E}{1+\nu} \varepsilon_x, \sigma_y = \frac{E}{1+\nu} \varepsilon_y, \sigma_z = \frac{E}{1+\nu} \varepsilon_z$$

At which, elastic modulus (E) of 200 GPa and Poisson's ratio (ν) of 0.3 was used for all samples and stress directions. For the *in-situ* stress evaluation the principal axes X and Y are treated as equal values to the probed radial component.

g. Magneto-optical Kerr effect (MOKE)

Magneto-optical Kerr effect (MOKE) microscopy is used for microscale-resolved imaging of the present magnetic structures. For this, a modified, high-resolution, bright-field microscope setup with polarisation optics is used. This includes a high-power LED as the light source and an electromagnet to apply homogeneous magnetic fields to the sample. By positioning the light source eccentrically in the back focal plane, longitudinal MOKE sensitivity is achieved [60]. Differential imaging is then employed to extract the weak MOKE contrast [61]. Furthermore, to minimise the impact of sample displacement caused by the applied external magnetic field, images are acquired by switching from positive to negative fields, as detailed by Jovičević-Klug et al. (2021, 2022) [34,51]. Additional image post-processing is carried out to remove topographical and illumination artefacts, as described in [51]. Local magnetization hysteresis were acquired by integrating the MOKE signal with step-wise externally applied magnetic field applied along the MOKE sensitivity axis. The hysteresis were also normalized by the maximum intensity value of the hysteresis series, which, in the case of the full hysteresis, is determined as magnetic saturation (M_s).

h. Atomic Force Microscopy mode Magnetic Force Microscopy (AFM-MFM)

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) in magnetic force microscopy (MFM) mode was used to measure the static magnetic domain structure of the samples under investigation. This non-contact scanning force method directly measures the presence and distribution of the magnetic fields emitted by remanent magnetic domain states. Magnetic domains are imaged by measuring the static magnetic interactions between the tip (composed of 30% nickel and 70% iron) and the sample as the cantilever is slowly scanned over the sample surface [62]. The AFM-MFM measurements were carried out in an Oxford Instruments Cypher Environmental System in a dry nitrogen gas environment.

3. Results and Discussion

a. Inside EN X17CrNi16-2: From Microstructure to Residual Stress Evolution

The detailed microstructure with thermodynamic modelling was performed in our previous study Jovičević-Klug et al. 2026 [1]; however, a concise summary is provided here in order to correlate the microstructure with the effects and results on dimensional stability, mechanical properties and magnetism. The XRD phase analysis in vol. % (Rietveld refinement) showed in control sample MSS-C the presence of retained austenite (FCC) with 17.8%, martensite (BCC/BCT) 74.1%, carbide groups of $M_{23}C_6$ 2.5%, M_7C_3 2.6% and M_3C_2 3% (Figure 2a red colour, Figure 2b). MSS-24 h *ex-situ* (Figure 2a blue colour, Figure 2c) had presence of FCC 0.5%, BCC/BCT 90.6%, $M_{23}C_6$ 3%, M_7C_3 2.8% and M_3C_2 3.1%. With compare to MSS-24 h *in-situ* (Figure 3g) had presence of 0.5% FCC, 90.3% BCC/BCT, 3% $M_{23}C_6$, 2.9% M_7C_3 and 3.3% M_3C_2 . The next sample MSS-8 h (Figure 2a green colour, Figure 2d) showed presence of FCC phase 0.8%, martensite 90.6%, $M_{23}C_6$ 3.3%, M_7C_3 2.5% and M_3C_2 2.8%. The last observed sample (Figure 2a purple colour, Figure 2e), MSS-multicycling (8 h CP followed by 6 h room temperature, followed by 8 h CP), showed the presence of 0.7% FCC, 91.4% BCC/BCT, 2.7% $M_{23}C_6$, 2.6% M_7C_3 and 2.6% M_3C_2 . Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showed that microstructural and phase changes also affect matrix distortion. KAM maps show that MSS-C retains high local distortion around FCC due to phase retransformation and stresses from α -martensite, while MSS-24 h exhibits a more uniform and overall higher misorientation, suggesting greater lattice strain. Both main samples (MSS-C and MSS-24 h) contain low-misorientation regions (more frequent in MSS-C), linked to prior austenite grains with low C and high Cr, which are larger and less distorted (ferrite-like). CP promotes further transformation of these grains into finer martensite through a CAR mechanism [1,63]: ferrite-like martensite destabilizes, transforms to retained austenite during tempering, and then to tertiary martensite. This produces fine α -martensite without requiring ϵ -martensite, though the process can be heterogeneous. EBSD confirms limited ϵ -martensite and shows Cr-enriched boundaries that act as nucleation sites for $Cr_{23}C_6$ carbides, forming thick carbide rims.

Figure 2: a) The spider diagram shows the distribution of phases in different samples in vol. %. Where M in carbides are Cr and Fe elements. B-e) the micrographs for all samples MSS-C (b), MSS-24 h (c), MSS-8 h (d) and MSS-multicycling (e). f-g) APT reconstructions, separated into matrix (Fe,Ni), carbide-forming metals (Cr, Mn, Mo), carbon clusters (C_n), and CrN positions, for the f) MSS-C and g) MSS-24 h specimens.

The nanostructure of the alloys was studied using APT. Figure 2f,g shows APT reconstructions of f) the MSS-C specimen and g) an MSS- 24h specimen. The reconstructed volumes are separated into the

main matrix metals (Fe, Ni), the carbide-forming metals (Cr, Mn, Mo), carbon positions (as clusters C_n for $n \leq 3$), and CrN positions. CrN was the most significant N-bearing species, with deconvolution of N^+/Si^{++} showing negligible N, and only a very small N^{++} peak appearing in the mass spectrum. The MSS-C specimen comprises both retained austenite and martensite, whereas the MSS-24 h specimen consists solely of martensite. In both materials, nanoscale plate-shaped carbides are observed within martensite grains. The plates have thickness ≈ 5 nm and diameters ≈ 50 nm, but the limited number of plates visible in the reconstructed volume prevent measurement of accurate size distributions. All carbides are found with elevated C, N, and Mo content, and in the MSS-24 h, sample, are also found to have with significantly increased Cr and Mn content. These findings support the hypothesis that CP enhances solute diffusion, promoting the formation of more highly alloyed carbides upon tempering, particularly for carbide-forming elements (C, Cr, Mn, Mo, and most likely N).

Ex-situ measurements were done by in-house XRD in order to estimate the surface micro-residual stress accurately. Surface micro-residual stress measurements (Figure 3a–b) revealed complex dynamics and interdependency between microstructure changes and residual stresses. All five of the tested groups predominantly have more surface micro-residual compressive stresses. However, some of them have changes in the values and nature of the surface micro-residual stresses, which are either more tensile or more compressive than those of MSS-C. The MSS-24 h *ex-situ* group (Figure 3a, blue colour) shows a trend towards higher compressive surface micro-residual stresses in all directions (37–90%) compared to the MSS-C control group. Compared to the MSS-24 h *in-situ* group, the MSS-C group had roughly 17% more compressive stresses in the 0° direction. In the other two directions (45° and 90°), the trend was towards more tensile surface micro-residual stresses. The possible explanation for the difference in holding time between the two groups is the crystallographic effects, such as grain orientation, surface-to-subsurface effects and phase heterogeneity [64,65]. The direct correlation could be due to phase heterogeneity in relation to the different types of martensite (α and ϵ), and the simple selection of the location of the inclusions. This means that in the MSS-24 h *ex-situ* group, the selected area had a higher concentration of α -martensite, and in the MSS-24 h *in-situ* group, the selected area had a higher concentration of ϵ -martensite. When comparing the XRD phase results, it was found that there was only 0.3% martensite in both the MSS-24 h groups. This indicates that a crystallographic change must have occurred within the same phase. This can be directly correlated to the proposed CAR mechanism by Jovičević-Klug et al. 2023 [63], where CP changes successfully suppress changes of ϵ -martensite back to austenite (newly reverted austenite).

Figure 3: Measured surface micro-residual stresses of a) MSS-C (control), MSS-24 h *ex-situ*, MSS-24 h *in-situ* samples and b) MSS-8 h and MSS-multicycling samples, all in directions of 0° , 45° and 90° , accordingly.

The observation of surface micro-residual stresses in these three groups also confirms the presence of ϵ -martensite in the CP groups. This is indicated by lower surface residual stresses compared to α -martensite, which exhibits more pronounced compressive stresses. Additionally, the increased number of defects in the crystal lattice and the elevated precipitation levels observed in both groups point to this possibility. Observation of surface micro-residual stresses in groups MSS-8h and MSS-multicycling showed lower values than the other three groups (Figure 3b). These values are more indicative of tensile stresses. This correlation can be directly attributed to the higher presence of the

FCC phase. No direct relationships were identified between the different orientations and their corresponding residual stresses. The observations clearly showed that a longer CP holding time is correlated with higher micro-residual compressive stresses, and that CP has a strong impact on these stresses. These stresses then affect dimensional stability and microhardness cumulatively. Groups with more pronounced changes (MSS-C, MSS-24 h *ex-situ* and MSS-24 h *in-situ*) were also chosen for advanced observations of the development of surface micro-residual stresses using POLDI.

Figure 4: Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs of samples investigated with POLDI: MSS-C (a-d), MSS-24 h *ex-situ* (e-h) and MSS-24 h *in-situ* (i-l). Where a, e, i show the band contrast maps from electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) mapping, b, f, j show the phase maps obtained with EBSD, c, g, k composite elemental maps obtained with electron dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) and d, h, l the inverted pole figure (IPF) obtained with EBSD.

The overall microstructure determined with EBSD (see Figure 4) indicates the clear refinement of the microstructure with the application of CP (regardless if *in-situ* or *ex-situ*). This particularly seen with the significantly larger martensitic laths for the MSS-C sample presented in Figure 4d. The phase mapping confirms the presence of the FCC austenite phase in all samples, at which the average fraction is around 2.5 % for both CP samples, while the fraction is about 11% for the MSS-C sample (Figure 4b, 4f, 4j). The local EDS chemical probing does not display any significant chemical variation between samples and that local chemical differences are related to residual delta ferrite (example in Figure 4g) and local manganese sulphides and larger M_3C_2 carbides (example in Figure 4g and 4k as blue and green, respectively). These specific samples investigated with EBSD are the identical samples probed with POLDI, so these samples also serve as a correlative perspective for the evaluation of the POLDI-derived stress results with the microstructural features.

b. Mechanical properties: Microhardness

Figure 5 shows the microhardness results, which reveal a slight (3%) increase (487 ± 5 HV) for the MSS-24 *ex-situ* and *in-situ* (490 ± 3 HV) group and decrease for MSS-8 h (379 ± 12 HV) and MSS-multicycling (371 ± 11 HV) groups by roughly 20% compared to control group MSS-C (475 ± 5 HV).

The increased microhardness observed after CP in MSS is thought to be due to the efficient transformation of retained austenite (FCC phase) into the BCC/BCT phase, as evidenced by the microstructure and our previous studies [1,63]. Furthermore, the increase in microhardness may also be related to increased carbide nucleation and transformation to carbides, which also inherently reduces tensile residual stresses. However, the decrease in microhardness in the MSS-C, MSS-8 h and MSS-multicycling groups can be well correlated to the higher presence of RA and lower presence

of $M_{23}C_6$ carbides. In the MSS-24 h groups (*ex*- and *in-situ*), the increase in hardness can be correlated not only to the matrix but also to the evolution of $M_{23}C_6$ carbides [1,63].

Figure 5: The results of the microhardness test for all groups with any changes noted. Six measurements were taken for each group to ensure reproducibility of the results, with the standard deviation included.

c. Magnetic behaviour

The probing of the MSS with and without CP using MOKE indicate a considerable change in the magnetic behaviour and properties. The MOKE-derived hysteresis (Figure 6a) indicates a strong modification of the coercivity of the material, enhanced by 24 h CP from 20 mT to 65 mT (see insert in Figure 6a). Additionally, the overall low-field magnetization evolution is considerably modified that results in the formation of a clear square-like opening in the hysteresis that is a result of the changed susceptibility in the region of the remanent magnetization (at 0 mT applied external magnetic field). The susceptibility change could be related to the change of the exchange coupling in the matrix phase, i.e. martensitic phase. In contrast the MSS-C sample displays a fairly closed hysteresis opening with no prominent formation of the low-field plateau in the range of remanent magnetization. With progressively higher fields over 100 mT, the MSS-24 h *ex-situ* sample closes the loop and the magnetization change follows a similar linear dependency with applied field as observed also for MSS-C sample.

Figure 6: a) MOKE-derived magnetic hysteresis of the MSS-C and MSS-24 h *ex-situ* samples displaying significant differences in the magnetic properties. b) MOKE-derived half minor loop of the magnetic response of the different samples displaying the clear and consistent effect of applied CP on the modification of the magnetic susceptibility and coercivity.

Similar to the 24h sample, the MSS-8 h and MSS-multicycling also show a wide square hysteresis opening and offset in the magnetic saturation (see half of minor loop in Figure 6b). However, the other two samples display a slightly wider opening and correspondingly higher coercivity as seen from Figure 6b, where MSS-multicycling present the widest opening. This is postulated to be related to the reduced residual stress state as presented in Figure 3. But all the samples display similar high-field susceptibility. This indicates that the overall susceptibility of the magnetic matrix, assumed to be mostly related to magnetization rotation, rather than domain wall motion, is unchanged by the application of CP. Consequentially, it is suggested that the change in the magnetization response must be mostly related to the pinning of the domain walls and changes in the local exchange coupling in the magnetic martensitic matrix, which is to be further elucidated with MOKE and AFM-MFM microscopy.

The MOKE imaging of the magnetic MSS-C sample compared to MSS-24 h *ex-situ* confirms the identified change in the magnetic response. As seen from Figure 7, the magnetization switching on a local level is slower for the MSS-24 h *ex-situ* sample compared to the MSS-C sample. The localized images indicate that the initial minor spontaneous magnetization switching is related to individual martensitic laths (marked with yellow arrows in Figure 7), which is potentially related to the favourable crystallographic alignment of the laths with their magnetic easy axis to the applied magnetic field direction (horizontal axis).

Figure 7: Series of high-magnification MOKE images with applied external magnetic field of MSS-C and MSS-24 h *ex-situ* samples. The direction of applied field and MOKE sensitivity are aligned horizontally. The yellow arrows mark the local regions displaying the initial spontaneous magnetization switching at low magnetic fields.

This explanation is also confirmed by larger-view MOKE imaging (see Figure S1 and S2). However, the progression of the magnetization switching is more segmented in the case of the MSS-24 h *ex-situ* sample, indicating that the changed coercivity is related to the interlath magnetic domain exchange coupling rather than intralath exchange between the larger primary regions of the martensitic laths. This is further confirmed by the magnetization change at higher fields (100 mT for MSS-C and 150 mT for MSS-24 h *ex-situ*). However, based on EBSD, the martensitic primary laths are considerably more internally segmented (see Figure 4), which could be the additional reason for increased magnetization pinning and thus increased coercivity and also explains the spontaneous segmented magnetization switching. The trend with applied CP on magnetization behaviour is also confirmed with MOKE microscopy to be similar for the MSS-8 h and MSS-multicycling (see Figures S3-S6).

Static (no-external applied field) AFM-MFM, presented in Figure 8, elucidates this further. The in-plane magnetization probing identifies a stark difference in the local remanent state of the martensitic laths. The magnetic domains are shown to be on average considerably smaller for the MSS-24 h *ex-situ* sample ($0.19 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{m}$) compared to the MSS-C one ($0.29 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{m}$). This does not include the sporadically found larger magnetic domains in MSS-C ($0.78 \pm 0.11 \mu\text{m}$) that are formed seldomly in specific regions of the material due to lack of segmentation of the martensitic laths (see EBSD data in Figure 4). The topography and surface artefacts are confirmed to not affect the domain constructs detected with AFM-MFM as presented in Figure S7. In addition, the MSS-24 h *ex-situ* sample displays more pronounced coupling of the domains into larger patches that show the interconnectivity is associated to the primary martensitic lath form. This supports the Kronmüller framework-based

assumption that the inherent magnetization pinning caused by the refinement of the martensitic grains and inherent increase in exchange coupling caused by residual stress changes modify the overall coercivity of the MSS material.

Figure 8: AFM-MFM images of in-plane magnetization of the MSS-C and MSS-24 h *ex-situ* samples.

d. Unravelling the time-dependent mechanism of CP with the help of *in-situ* observations

All samples before the *in-situ* experiments show similar presence of martensite and austenite as well as carbides of M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$ type as the main phases, consistent with prior literature [1,63,66]. Minor sample-to-sample differences exist in terms of the relative intensities of individual peaks of specific crystallographic planes of the martensite matrix, related to the random probed sample volume (see Figure S6). The WOMBAT data indicates no significant phase changes occur during both CP and tempering stages of any of the samples. The most significant changes are related to the martensitic matrix that displays changes in the peak shapes, particularly those of planes with mixed and higher numbered indices. This is already observed with the exposure of the samples to cryogenic temperatures that after 24 h present minor peak shifts of the higher index planes, i.e. $\{411\}$, see Figure S7. However, the CP sample with applied magnetic field displays considerably less prominent shifts and changes of the diffractogram compared to the conventional CP sample.

To understand this relation, *in-situ* neutron diffraction is performed during the exposure to CP of both samples. The subtle changes in the peak positions were traced and a representative trace for the $\{411\}$ peak is plotted in Figure 9a. The peak position tracing reveals a significant difference in the evolution of the lattice spacing with CP exposure time with and without application of magnetic field. As seen from Figure 9a, the case with no magnetic field displays a significant hill, while the case with magnetic field displays a generally continuous increase of the diffraction angle with exposure time. These variable changes in the peak position shifts suggest that the CP effect on the lattice and local strains can be controlled through the application of a magnetic field during CP. Additionally, the data indicates an important perspective on the maximum effect of CP on the lattice changes. This is suggested to be related to the pronounced maxima of the tracing curve for the CP case without magnetic field that is formed after approximately 14 h. Interestingly, the CP case with magnetic field also shows a slight dip in the same time range, but in this case as a local minima. This suggests that the lattice changes during CP are guided by internally-regulated kinetics of relaxation that is in-line with proposed theories and support the research indicating that CP has an optimal exposure time [4,38,67–69]. This also stipulates that for this particular steel the optimal CP time is in the range of 10–14 h (when conducted without applied magnetic field) and that CP in-fact expands the lattice rather than quenches as expected by traditional theory. However, this data also indicates that with applied external energy, i.e. magnetic field, the CP can be controlled by manipulating the evolution of the lattice changes, which can have significant impact on the final strain and relaxation of the material.

Additionally, the changes in the evolution could have potential impact or originate from the modified redistribution of the alloying elements and their mobility [70].

Figure 9: (a): Traced peak position of the nominal peak for the {411} planes from neutron diffraction with time during exposure to cryogenic temperatures, including cooling to and heating from the target 77 K cryogenic temperature. (b) Traced peak position of the nominal peak for the {411} planes for all the samples during the tempering procedure, including the heating and cooling part.

It should be noted that for both samples, all the martensitic peaks show a similar trend of peak position change with exposure time, as presented in Figure S7. However, they are different in absolute magnitude due to the different lattice planes and their d-spacings. Consequentially, it can be concluded that the overall effect of CP on the lattice is homogeneous in a volumetric sense. However, as can be seen from Figure S7, the shift intensities are not proportional to the d-spacing/ 2θ values, suggesting that the CP effect is selective to the density of individual planes and possibly related to the availability of more mobile carbon atoms in the octahedral interstitial spaces.

For further evaluation of the effect of CP on the effective change of the lattice and activation of the migration and redistribution of the alloying elements, the subsequent tempering step is also probed in an *in-situ* manner. While the tempering stage would be interesting for probing the evolution of the carbides and the change of their volume fraction, this was not conducted in this study. This is due to the attenuation of the beam by the window of the furnace used for tempering, that causes the characteristic peaks of the carbides to be indistinguishable from the background. The comparison of the state before and after tempering (see Figure S8) indicates similar diffractogram changes for all samples. The most prominent changes are registered in regards to relative intensities of individual reflections that is related to slight narrowing of the peaks, indicating grain refinement as well as reduction of micro-strains. The latter, is particularly visible by the stark changes in the shape, intensity and skewness of the {411} peaks at 129° . However, the other peaks also show a similar change as presented in Figure S9 for the case of the {301} peak for both CP samples as an example. With *in-situ* tracing of the peak positions, as presented in Figure 9b, the strong shifts of all the diffraction peaks due to tempering are confirmed. The samples display generally a similar evolution with tempering. However, there are 2 major differences. Firstly, the cooling and heating regime causes sudden lattice changes for the MSS-C and CP samples, while for CP sample with magnetic field, the lattice changes are more continuous. Secondly, during the tempering itself, the CP sample shows slightly stronger shifts, accompanied by higher fluctuations, compared to the other two samples, indicating that the tempering might be more affecting the microstrain and microstructural changes in the CP sample. Interestingly, all the samples after cooling back to RT, display slightly lower or similar peak positions than before the tempering and display much closer peak positions between each other as before the tempering. Altogether, this data indicates that CP has an effect on changing the lattice during CP itself as well as with tempering. However, the application of additional magnetic field during the CP seems to induce further changes that stipulate significant modification of the lattice evolution with CP as well as subsequent tempering.

Figure 10: POLDI-based results of the in-situ evaluated stress evolution along one of the radial axes during a) CP and b) tempering. In a) the data is also presented with an applied smoothing based of the Savitzky-Golay filtering with 20 points window. In b) the insert displays the stress data with higher temporal resolution in the tempering plateau region with the same axes as that of the main graph. c) presents the 3-axis stress state for all 3 investigated samples before and after CP and tempering. The X and Y represent the two orthogonal radial axes, while Z represents the axial axis of the sample.

On a separate note, the austenite fraction is changed with tempering for the CP cases by reducing its fraction by 2% and 4% for the CP samples without and with magnetic field, respectively. While for the MSS-C case, the austenite fraction remained unchanged even after tempering. This only minor change of austenite fraction with both CP and tempering for all the samples, indicates that there are potentially differences of these samples with the samples from previous research despite using the same steel grade and treatment conditions. A possible explanation could be that the neutron irradiation is influencing the development of the austenite phase as well as disabling the progression of special transformations such as austenite reversion transformation (ART) and CAR as observed through conventional *ex-situ* investigations [1,63]. The limited effect of CP on the austenite reduction could be a result also of the considerably slower cooling rate compared to conventional CP direct immersion and nebulization procedures that have cooling rates about 10-100x faster. As given by prior literature, the rate of cooling can have an impact on the efficiency of CP and connected changes in the phase fraction [4,71–73].

To confirm the proposed effect of CP on the development of residual stress in an *in-situ* manner during CP as well as after tempering, the samples were investigated with neutron-based time of-flight diffractometer, POLDI (see Methods subsection e for more details). The *in-situ* results confirm that temporal evolution of residual stresses is indeed induced with CP as seen from Figure 9a. Furthermore, the results confirm that a dip-like maximum change during CP follows a similar trend as observed with WOMBAT XRD. To provide a clearer visualization of the dip and evolution trend, a Savitzky-Golay filter was applied to the raw data (see red curve in Figure 9a). The POLDI results indicate that the dip is optimal in the range of 9-13 h during CP. This coincides well with the WOMBAT results that also indicate that a higher compressive character should be developed based on the total lattice change trend. Considering that the translation between lattice change and residual stress match

well, the effect of the magnetic field on the lack of pronounced change during the CP instigates that the internal stresses also do not change strongly. This is postulated to originate from the quenching of the material in the radial directions by the magnetic field that in turn limits the stress evolution. However, this could also indicate that the out-of-plane/axial stresses are dominating and compensating the lack of the average dilatation from the radial axes. Consequentially, the MSS-24 h *in-situ* mag sample is proposed to essentially display the irreversible lattice changes that are considered to originate solely from the non-elastic changes caused by local phase changes and changes in the local chemistry, i.e. migration of alloying elements, which can be associated to the net stress change observed by POLDI. This explanation is also in line with the change in stress state of the material during heating and cooling (global lattice expansion and contraction) that is correlated well with the change in the peak shifts determined with WOMBAT. This also applies to the *in-situ* measurement during tempering for all samples as presented in Figure 9b. The slight changes can be also observed from the 2D spectral images presented in Figure S10a, where the enhancement of individual bands can be seen with the progression of the CP and tempering steps.

The *in-situ* POLDI results during tempering strongly indicate a pronounced effect of the temperature on the lattice strain/stress state, while during tempering itself the changes are minute and relatively consistent for all samples as presented in Figure 9b. Nonetheless, high temporal segmentation of the tempering plateau indicates an initial spontaneous rising of the stresses at the onset of reaching the tempering temperature. This is not an artefact of temperature overshooting as the temperature was regulated with average variation of 0.1 K with maximum overshooting of 0.3 K for all samples. The initial rising of the stresses is thus postulated to originate from the recovery and recrystallization processes during the initial stage of tempering that can induce changes in stress levels that is physically traced in reduced hardness for MSS in general [74]. Interestingly, this process is postponed to later times for the CP samples, which is more prominent for the *in-situ* sample (0.4 h offset) compared to the *ex-situ* one (0.2 h offset). After the initial rise, the stress levels stabilize and show no other prominent feature. However, with tempering, the 2D POLDI spectrums in Figure S10a do indicate that the band become narrower, which indicate a more refined and segmented structure, which seems to progress with tempering time. This is also observable from the 1D fit of the POLDI data (see Figure S10b), which is supported by the EBSD investigation of the samples (see Figure 4).

After the tempering is completed, the samples indicate a change in the stress state from before tempering and also between the samples. However, this can be an artefact of the fast scanning and offset in the relative position of stress state during the heating and cooling. To avoid such misinterpretation, the intermediate states of the samples before and after CP and tempering were measured at room temperature in a 3-axis cartesian space at which Z represents the axial direction and X and Y the radial axes. These results, presented in Figure 9c, confirm that both CP and tempering influence the stress state of the samples in a volumetric and incommensurate manner. Additionally, the results indicate that the *in-situ* and *ex-situ* CP samples display difference in the effect of CP on the initial austenitized state. This is assumed to originate from the varying initial stress state of the samples that seem to vary from sample to sample (including when comparing with MSS-C), which can be a result of the machining of the samples and the variable microstructure in the samples, related to the randomized martensitic lath arrangements (see EBSD data in Figure 4). Regardless of this, the resulting state after tempering is shown to be nearly identical for the two CP samples that are different from the MSS-C sample. Furthermore, the CP samples show similar values between X and Y, while the MSS-C sample displays an unevenness between the axes. This infers that CP enables homogeneous relaxation and redistribution of stresses in the samples and that the overall stress state is consistently modified, regardless of prior stress history. In this regard it is also clear that CP enables predominantly tensile bulk stresses, which correlates with the compressive surface stresses as determined with in-house XRD (see Figure 3). However, the relative stress levels do not match perfectly 1:1, which can be a result of the physical difference of samples related to their shape for the POLDI and in-house XRD measurements, which can impose differences in the evolution of stresses from bulk to surface.

4. Conclusions and Future Outlook

This study investigated the effect of cryogenic processing (CP) with and without exposure to a magnetic field of up to 5 T on the microstructure of MSS EN X17CrNi16-2 steel, compared to the effect of conventional heat treatment. Advanced microscopy, neutron measurements and microhardness

testing were used to examine micro-residual stresses, magnetic behaviour and mechanical properties, providing rare insight into the time-dependent mechanisms behind CP:

1. CP significantly reduced retained austenite in MSS EN X17CrNi16-2 steel while increasing martensite content to over 90%, leading to greater lattice strain and a finer, more uniform microstructure. These changes, confirmed by XRD, SEM, and EBSD, suggest that CP promotes martensitic transformation through, improving dimensional stability and influencing the steel's mechanical and magnetic properties. APT revealed that CP induces the formation of alloy-rich nanoscale carbides within martensite. This indicates that solute diffusion is enhanced during tempering following CP.
2. *Ex-situ* XRD revealed that longer CP increased compressive residual stresses, likely due to martensitic phase transformations and crystallographic changes. These stresses had a significant impact on the steel's dimensional stability and microhardness.
3. MOKE confirmed that MSS-24 h *ex-situ* exhibited more segmented magnetization switching and higher switching fields, indicating that increased coercivity arises primarily from interlath exchange coupling and enhanced magnetization pinning due to internally segmented martensitic laths, a trend also consistently seen across MSS-8 h and MSS-multicycling samples.
4. Static AFM-MFM showed that MSS-24 h *ex-situ* exhibited smaller but more interconnected magnetic domains than MSS-C, confirming that martensitic lath refinement and stress-induced exchange coupling govern remanent magnetization behaviour and coercivity.
5. *In-situ* WOMBAT XRD analysis showed that CP modifies lattice evolution. All samples exhibited similar overall changes to the diffractogram, while *in-situ* peak tracking reveals that CP with an applied magnetic field leads to more continuous lattice changes, stronger peak shifts and higher fluctuations during tempering than MSS-C and CP alone. This indicates enhanced microstructural sensitivity; however, all samples converge to similar lattice states after cooling. *In-situ* POLDI measurements additionally confirmed the correlative results from WOMBAT XRD and *ex-situ* XRD that confirms that CP introduces more homogeneous volumetric relaxation of internal stresses than MSS-C.
6. The study also reveals that for ferrous alloys, CP exposure (soaking time) of between 9 and 13 hours is considered as optimal for structural, stress and local chemical changes for the benefit of the final properties related to residual stresses and mechanical properties.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Patricia Jovičević-Klug: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing, Visualisation, Resources.

Matic Jovičević-Klug: Methodology, Validation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing, Visualisation.

Levi Tegg: Methodology, Validation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing, Visualisation.

James R. Hester: Methodology, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing.

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Julie M. Cairney: Writing-review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

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Data availability

The raw and processed data required to reproduce these findings are available from the corresponding author upon request.

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Declarations

Declaration of Ethics in publishing

Authors have followed the ethical guidelines stated in the Publishing Ethics Policy.

Declaration of competing interest

Authors declare no competing interest.

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Supplementary Materials

Operando Cryogenic Processing Effects on Residual Stress and Magnetism of X17CrNi16-2 Martensitic Stainless Steel for Energy Sector

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Supplementary Figure S1: Series of low-magnification MOKE images with applied external magnetic field of MSS-C sample. The direction of applied field and MOKE sensitivity are aligned horizontally.

Supplementary Figure S2: Figure Series of low-magnification MOKE images with applied external magnetic field of MSS-24 h *ex-situ* sample. The direction of applied field and MOKE sensitivity are aligned horizontally.

Supplementary Figure S3: Series of high-magnification MOKE images with applied external magnetic field of MSS-C sample. The direction of applied field and MOKE sensitivity are aligned horizontally.

Supplementary Figure S4: Series of high-magnification MOKE images with applied external magnetic field of MSS-24 h *ex-situ* sample. The direction of applied field and MOKE sensitivity are aligned horizontally

Supplementary Figure S5: Examples of AFM-MFM height and magnetic contrast mapping to illustrate the independence of the magnetic signal and contrast to the surface preparation and surface artefacts.

Supplementary Figure S6: The WOMBAT XRD indicates that there are minor differences in the relative intensities of the individual peaks of the specific crystallographic planes of the martensite matrix between samples, due to the random location and volume of the samples being probed.

Supplementary Figure S7: Comparison of the WOMBAT data of the two CP samples to visualize the minor peak shifts observed for the different planes, i.e. {411}, after CP.

Supplementary Figure S8: WOMBAT data presented in overlap per sample for direct comparison of the diffractograms before and after tempering.

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Supplementary Figure S9: Figure shows the case of the {301} peak shift for both CP samples before or after individual processing steps.

Supplementary Figure S10: a) Examples of spectral presentation of the 2D fitted POLDI data for the MSS 24 h *in-situ* sample during the different stages of the CP and tempering treatments presented with false colours based of Viridis colour scale. b) Examples of 1D fitting of POLDI data in a form of a diffractogram that is a result of the compression of the spectral data into a 1D dataset. The blue dots represent the raw compressed 1D POLDI data, the orange curve represents the 1D fitting of the data and the green curve represents the residual signal not covered by the fitted data. The data presents the evaluation of the stress state along the Y-axis of the MSS 24 h *in-situ* sample before and after individual treatment steps.